

THE ROLE OF FAIRY TALES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AND THE
TECHNIQUES OF USING FAIRY TALES IN MIDDLE SCHOOL FOR MORE
EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF THE LESSON AND MENTAL DEVELOPMENT
OF CHILDREN.

Tolipova Ozoda Zokir qizi

Teacher of the Department of Private Legal Sciences of the Jizzakh
Region Legal Technical

College. Jizzakh State Pedagogical University, second-year master's student.

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Abstract. In modern pedagogical practice, one of the challenges of modern school technology is to organize lessons more effectively and facilitate the learning process of children, while at the same time increasing the interest of the younger generation in learning. The main purpose of choosing middle class, children of this period remember better and faster and retain in their memory for a long time information, cases, incidents, faces, objects, facts, but not abstract definitions or descriptions. Younger schoolchildren memorize mechanically, without realizing the semantic connections in this material.

Key words: English language, fairy tales, student, individual, group, skills, methods and efficiency, middle class students and methods.

РОЛЬ СКАЗОК В ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ И ПРИЕМЫ
ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ СКАЗОК В СРЕДНЕЙ ШКОЛЕ ДЛЯ БОЛЕЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОЙ
ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ УРОКА И УМСТВЕННОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ДЕТЕЙ.

Аннотация. В современной педагогической практике одной из задач современной школьной технологии является более эффективная организация уроков и облегчение процесса обучения детей, одновременное повышение интереса подрастающего поколения к обучению. Основная цель выбора среднего класса - дети этого периода лучше и быстрее запоминают и надолго сохраняют в памяти информацию, случаи, происшествия, лица, предметы, факты, а не абстрактные определения или описания. Младшие школьники запоминают механически, не осознавая смысловых связей в этом материале.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, сказки, ученик, личность, группа, навыки, методы и эффективность, ученики среднего класса и методы.

Today, extensive work is being done to develop children's mental and physical abilities and organize lessons more effectively. When a child comes to school, the most important for him will be the following social motives: motives of self-improvement (which means to be developed, cultural) and self-determination motives (on completion of school, continue to study, and then work successfully). The child must be aware of the social significance of learning. The listed motives are the results of the influence of society (kindergarten, family). During the first school days, such an atmosphere sets children's positive attitude towards work and helps to recreate favorable conditions for learning. Younger schoolchildren most often live for today.

That is why it is of great importance in the educational process how competently short-term and long-term goals are set. The teacher must form a responsible attitude towards learning: it lies in the ability of the younger student to consciously subordinate his actions to relevant,

important goals and objectives. There are also personal motives: for example, motives of well-being (when a child wants to get a good grade at any cost, to earn praise). Younger schoolchildren experience a feeling of pride, an incredible surge when their teacher praises them. A teacher in a primary school has a huge educational impact. This is due to the fact that the teacher, from the very beginning of school, is a clear authority for children. The authority of the teacher is one of the most important prerequisites for teaching and education in primary school.

Educational activities in primary school, first of all, help in the development of mental processes of a child's cognition of the world around him through perceptions and sensations. Younger schoolchildren are distinguished by the fact that they see this world most acutely and freshly, and have a certain contemplative curiosity. One of the typical features of the perception of a junior schoolchild is low differentiation. Children of primary school age may make mistakes or not accurately differentiate similar objects in their perception. Another feature of the perception of students of this age is its close connection with what the child does.

At this level of mental development, perception correlates with actions in practice. If a child touches an object, takes it in its hands, makes some kind of manipulation, this means that it perceives it that way. Also, pronounced emotionality in the perception of children of primary school age is characteristic. Early days of universal education, primary school Chinese courses focused on the instrumental nature of language learning and emphasized the development of learning. Students' ability to read, write, listen, and speak; as for humanistic elements, such as literary education, teachers will adapt to the textbooks are selected and taught according to the text, and they are also supplemented by extracurricular reading.

Children's books are not new. From the perspective of teaching operations, although we did not necessarily use "children's books" in the past. This name, but Chinese teachers or library directors will also ask students to read children's books in school. Respectively, Those who teach often regard reading children's books as "extracurricular reading", that is, students read assigned books on their own outside of class or recommended book. Due to class time constraints, teachers or library directors usually do not specifically instruct students in reading. Extracurricular books, but students will be asked to do post-reading exercises in different forms, such as listing the basic information of reading materials. Materials (author, publisher, date of publication), excerpts, brief introduction, and feelings after reading, etc. This kind of children's book reading arrangement will not take up classroom time, and it can also monitor students' reading results.

Treating children's book reading as "extracurricular reading", due to students' lack of reading guidance, reading. Reading is very random, and a student's reading effectiveness often depends on the student's personal factors. Students who are interested in reading and have a high understanding of words, although they do not receive special guidance.

Fairy tales belong to a larger body of literature known as folktales. It is necessary to understand the importance of folktales in order to define "fairy tales." Arbuthnot (1976) described folktales as stories of anonymous origin that were handed down orally from generation to generation and contain various elements of a tribe or group of people such as superstitions, rituals and religious elements. Briggs and Wayne (1979) offer a similar definition. Folktales may be defined as stories of anonymous origin which form a part of the oral tradition of a tribe or people. Fairy stories are usually included within the larger category of folktales even though the authorship

of modern fairy stories is known. Adults may classify the stories as folktales but children call them fairy tales because of the magic, enchantment and wonder therein, (p. 15) Social anthropologists believe that folktales have acted to cement the belief systems and acceptable codes of behavior for a group of people.

This is the reason folk and fairy tales are found worldwide in children's fiction (Opie & Opie, 1974; Sutherland & Arbuthnot, 1977). In addition, striking similarities are found among the tales of different people. Opie and Opie (1974) hypothesized that people everywhere are faced with common human problems. It is difficult to arrive at a precise definition of "fairy tales." However, most experts in children's literature include the following elements in their definition: (1) fairy tales are more complex than folktales in theme or plot, (2) they contain magical elements, (3) the characters are usually witches, princes and princesses, fairies, etc., (4) they are unbelievable. In this study, the fairy tales that form the base of the curriculum meet the criteria listed above. All come 10 from the well known collection of Jacob and Wilhelm Grimm (Germany, 1815). The stories selected are listed as fairy tales in the work *The Classic Fairy Tales* by Opie and Opie (1974).

According to Favat (1977), in each fairy tale there is a hero or heroine who comes upon a person or animal of magical powers from whom he receives a magical device enabling him to attain his fortune or wishes as a reward for a good deed. The main character always struggles against the powers of evil or some deprivation, but comes out victorious in the end. The tales selected for this study contain this type of theme. Andre Favat (1977) studied children's interest in fairy tales. He was interested in cognitive development and found what he believed were similar characteristics in young children's thinking and fairy tales.

Favat studied the stories collected by Perrault and the Grimm brothers and integrated characteristics of these studies with the theory of intelligence proposed by Jean Piaget. Favat suggested the following characteristics were found in both child and tale: (1) Magic and the child. Children believe an object or place can magically be used to influence another object. This is related to Piaget's concept of "participation," in which beings or objects have a direct influence on one another even though there is no spatial contact or intelligible causal connection between them (p. 132). In fairy tales the characters often use thoughts and words to influence events. They wish for things and they occur.

Thus, summing up our research, we can note that the method of teaching English in primary school is acquiring a new round of development through the teaching methods we have described; the results and materials of this study are of practical value for practicing English language teachers in primary schools and can be used by literally each of them; and, as we believe, the fairy-tale method we propose can bring a large number of positive results and improve the quality of teaching a foreign language in primary school.

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